

1 **Is SCENA a good approach for side-stream integrated treatment from an**
2 **environmental and economic point of view?**

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12 Nomenclature

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Abbreviation	Description
Al	Aluminium
AD	Anaerobic digestion
BOD	Biological oxygen demand
C	Carbon
CAPS	Chemically assisted primary sedimentation
COD	Chemical oxygen demand
DPAO	Denitrifying polyphosphate-accumulating organisms
EBPR	Enhanced biological phosphorus removal
Fe	Iron
FU	Functional unit
GHG	Greenhouse gas
GWP	Global warming potential
LCA	Life cycle assessment
LCC	Life cycle cost
LCI	Life cycle inventory
LCIA	Life cycle impact assessment
N	Nitrogen
P	Phosphorus
PAC	Poly-aluminium chloride
RBS	Rotating belt screen
SBFR	Sequencing batch fermentation reactor
SCENA	Short Cut Enhanced Nutrient Abatement
scSBR	Short-cut sequencing batch reactor
SDT	Sludge dynamic thickening
TS	Total solids
VFA	Volatile fatty acid
WAS	Waste secondary sludge
WWTP	Wastewater treatment plant

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15

16 **Abstract**

17 The environmental and economic benefits and burdens of including the first Short Cut Enhanced Nutrient
18 Abatement (SCENA) into a real municipal wastewater treatment plant were evaluated using life cycle
19 assessment (LCA) and life cycle cost (LCC). The implications of accomplishing nitrogen (N) removal and
20 phosphorus (P) recovery via nitrite in the side stream were assessed taking into account the actual effluent
21 quality improvement, the changes in the electricity and chemical consumption, N₂O, CO₂ and CH₄ emissions
22 and the effects of land application of biosolids, among others. In addition, a case-specific estimation of the P
23 availability when sludge is applied to land, therefore replacing conventional fertilizer, was performed.
24 Furthermore, to account for the variability in input parameters, and to address the related uncertainties,
25 Monte Carlo simulation was applied.

26 The analysis revealed that SCENA in the side stream is an economic and environmentally friendly solution
27 compared to the traditional plant layout with no side-stream treatment, thanks to the reduction of energy and
28 chemical use for the removal of N and P, respectively. The uncertainty analysis proved the validity of the
29 LCA results for global warming potential and impact categories related to the consumption of fossil-based
30 electricity and chemicals, while robust conclusions could not be drawn on freshwater eutrophication and
31 toxicity-related impact categories. Furthermore, three optimization scenarios were also evaluated proving
32 that the performance of the WWTP can be further improved by, for instance, substituting gravitational for
33 mechanical thickening of the sludge or changing the operational strategy to the chemically enhanced primary
34 treatment, although this second alternative will increase the operational cost by 5%. Finally, the outcomes
35 show that shifting P removal from chemical precipitation in the main line to biologically enhanced uptake in
36 the side stream is key to reducing chemicals use, thus the operational cost, and increasing the environmental
37 benefit of synthetic fertilizers replacement.

38

39 **Keywords**

40 Short Cut Enhanced Nutrient Abatement (SCENA); Side-stream treatment; Life cycle analysis (LCA); Life
41 cycle cost (LCC); Monte Carlo analysis; Sludge phosphorus availability.

42

43 **1. Introduction**

44 Within the last decade it has been required that wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) meet increasing
45 effluent quality standards at affordable cost. Separate treatment of the reject water resulting from dewatering
46 of anaerobic digested sludge at WWTP can be a solution for meeting higher load requirements or stricter
47 effluent standards regarding nitrogen (N) (Malamis et al. 2014). Regarding this issue, several technologies
48 have been developed and successfully implemented at full scale (Lackner et al. 2014). Among them, the
49 implementation of one-stage partial nitrification/anammox, also known as DEMON (Wett 2006), CANON
50 (Third et al. 2001) and OLAND (Kuai and Verstraete 1998), could positively contribute to the optimization
51 of the energy balance of WWTPs by minimizing energy for N removal. As an example, at the Strass WWTP,
52 DEMON in the side stream has reduced electricity consumed per kg of N removed by 44% (Schaubroeck et
53 al. 2015).

54 Furthermore, as a consequence of the growing awareness of the need to control phosphorus (P) emissions,
55 which is reflected in the increasingly stringent regulations (Gaterell et al. 2000), a boost was given to the
56 existing wastewater industry in order to increase its removal (Hukari et al. 2016). Until now, P has been
57 regarded more as a contaminant than a resource. This perspective has started to change in recent years, since
58 unlike N, P is a limited resource, whose recovery should be promoted as much as possible (Desmidt et al.
59 2015). However, the most common approach for removing phosphate from wastewater is metal salt
60 precipitation, which makes the precipitate unrecoverable for possible industrial processing into fertilizer (De-
61 Bashan and Bashan 2004, Melia et al. 2017, Torri et al. 2017).

62 In this regard, the recent introduction of Short-Cut Enhanced Nutrient Abatement (SCENA), for treatment of
63 nutrient-rich reject water, brings an important improvement because P can also be removed from reject water
64 by its enhanced bioaccumulation in the same system (Renzi et al. 2015). In fact, SCENA is a side-stream
65 technology, which combines via-nitrite ammonia oxidation (also known as short-cut nitrification) with
66 denitrifying enhanced biological phosphorus removal (EBPR) processes by the addition of external volatile
67 fatty acids (VFAs) produced on-site (Longo et al. 2015). In this process NH_4 is oxidized to NO_2 , which is
68 then reduced to gaseous N_2 by denitrifying polyphosphate-accumulating organisms (DPAO), hence resulting
69 in the potential production of a high added value product (Frison et al. 2016).

70 As a holistic environmental assessment approach, life cycle assessment (LCA) (ISO 2006) has proved to act
71 as a valuable tool in evaluating the environmental aspects and improvement opportunities of wastewater

72 systems (Corominas et al. 2013, Yoshida et al. 2013, Zang et al. 2015), including most impacts upon the
73 environment, which helps avoid the risk of ‘problem transfer’ (Guinée 2002). In a LCA study Rodriguez-
74 Garcia et al. (2014) compared different side-stream technologies. The authors emphasized that
75 eutrophication impacts can be significantly reduced by using side-stream technologies, while global warming
76 potential was only marginally reduced. Moreover, there is a certain consensus on the trade-offs between
77 higher N removal achieved by implementation of side-stream technologies and increased direct emissions,
78 with the results being very sensitive to the N₂O emission balance (Schaubroeck et al. 2015, Hauck et al.
79 2016).

80 Furthermore, the evaluation of appropriate schemes for wastewater treatment has to consider not only
81 environmental concerns but also economic aspects (Corominas et al. 2013) (e.g., investment, operation and
82 maintenance costs). In this respect life cycle cost (LCC) (Fabrycky and Blanchard 1991) is a useful
83 framework for assessing the economic sustainability of different wastewater treatment schemes over the
84 whole life span of the plant.

85 Thus, to investigate the holistic environmental and economic life cycle implications of N and P removal
86 through SCENA, this study aims to answer the following questions: i) Is the SCENA system
87 environmentally and economically sustainable? ii) How does SCENA improve the environmental and
88 economic performance of a real WWTP? To provide answers to our questions preliminary results of the first
89 full-scale SCENA system were analysed.

90

91 **2. Material and methods**

92 **2.1. Goal and scope**

93 The goal of the study was to assess the environmental and economic benefits of implementing SCENA in the
94 side-stream treatment of reject water at a real municipal WWTP; the Carbonera facilities (Treviso, Northern
95 Italy).

96 The system boundary included the WWTP operation with all its associated background processes, such as
97 provision of energy and production and transportation of chemicals, effluent discharge and direct gaseous
98 emissions deriving from the treatment process as well as composting and posterior land application.

99 Regarding the construction phase, only data from SCENA were accounted for in the assessment, as the rest
100 of the facilities remain the same. Upstream wastewater collection and transportation were not included in the

101 analysis although it has been shown that the sewer system makes an important contribution in comparison to
102 the WWTP (Risch et al. 2015); however, these impacts would be the same for each scenario, and are
103 therefore not relevant for comparative purposes.

104 The functional unit (FU) has been based on the reduction of eutrophication as defined by the CML
105 methodology (Guinée 2002): 1 kg PO₄³⁻ eq. removed. This approach helps with the comparison of different
106 influent wastewater loads by weighting the main pollutants, and reflects the service that the WWTP delivers:
107 the removal of contaminants (e.g., chemical oxygen demand, N and P) (Rodriguez-Garcia et al. 2014).

108

109 **2.2. Treatment options**

110 The flow diagram of the SCENA system implemented at the Carbonera WWTP is shown in Fig. 1, and an
111 elaborate description of the plant is given in section A of the supplementary file.

112 In Table 1 are reported the different treatment configurations of the WWTP under investigation. The
113 environmental and economic performance of the plant with no additional nutrient removal from reject water
114 (2015, scenario 0) was compared with the new plant layout (2016, scenario 1) in which the full-scale
115 SCENA is operating in the side stream. Additionally, three different alternative configurations (scenarios
116 2A-C) for the optimization of the SCENA system and the whole plant performance were simulated. Since
117 the success of EBPR depends on the constant availability of VFAs, the objective of the optimization was to
118 increase the organic loading rate of the SBFR in order to improve and stabilize the VFAs production, which
119 could enable higher rates of biological nutrient removal in the short-cut sequencing batch reactor (scSBR).
120 To do so, in scenario 2A sludge dynamic thickening (SDT) was considered as an effective technology to
121 increase the total solids (TS) concentration of the mixed sludge by up to 5%; in scenario 2B, chemically
122 assisted primary sedimentation (CAPS), consisting of adding chemicals in order to increase the coagulation,
123 flocculation and sedimentation of raw wastewater, was simulated. The application of CAPS was chosen
124 since it does not require any further significant structural intervention, thus saving investment costs and
125 footprint (De Feo et al. 2012); finally, in scenario 2C, the primary sedimentation tank was replaced by a
126 rotating belt screen (RBS) system in order to improve the performance of primary treatment (removal of TS
127 up to 70%) without use of chemicals (Paulsrud et al. 2014). The CAPS system, apart from TS and chemical
128 oxygen demand (COD), can enhance also the removal of P from wastewater. As a consequence scenario 2B
129 will be characterized by a lower effluent discharge for P, despite the fact that all scenarios have the same

130 effluent discharge limits. However, considering the increasingly lower discharge limit policies with regard to
131 P or the spreading of the effluent load tax incentives in Europe (consider, for example, the case of Germany)
132 this scenario is interesting to study for its potential future application. The inventory assumptions for
133 scenarios 2A-C are summarized in section C of the supplementary file.

134

135 **2.3. Inventory data**

136 **2.3.1. Operational data and background processes**

137 Operational data (e.g., water and sludge flow/composition, energy consumption, chemical usage etc.) were
138 directly gathered in-situ and provided by the company that operates the plant from the daily log results of
139 2015 and 2016, unless mentioned otherwise. Data for the processes of the background system (production of
140 electricity, chemicals and N- and P-based fertilisers) come from the ecoinvent v3.1 database (cut-off system
141 model) (Weidema et al. 2013). A complete discussion of the inventory data collection is given in section B
142 of the supplementary file.

143

144 **2.3.1. Fertilizer replacement**

145 The benefits of sludge application on arable land can be accounted by crediting for the avoided production of
146 mineral N and P fertilizer. The selection of the replacement ratio at which the N and P in sludge replace
147 mineral fertilizer is challenging and it was shown to be important for the overall LCA results (Heimersson et
148 al. 2017). Contrary to N, the availability of P in chemical and biological solids is an area of on-going
149 research (Menezes-Blackburn et al. 2016), although it is largely accepted that the P in solids containing high
150 levels of aluminium (Al) or iron (Fe) is less available for uptake by plants (Qin et al. 2015). The reason is
151 that metal phosphates (e.g., iron and aluminium phosphates) are unavailable to plants (Melia et al. 2017,
152 Torri et al. 2017), since they are among the most difficult of soil compounds from which to solubilize P,
153 which makes the P removed by metal salt precipitation unrecoverable for possible industrial processing into
154 fertilizer (De-Bashan and Bashan 2004).¹ The substitution should be based on the amount of mineral
155 fertilizer that is actually replaced rather than theoretically, as outlined in several recent LCA studies (Niero et
156 al. 2014, Heimersson et al 2016, 2017). Thus, in this study case specific P replacement ratios were estimated

¹ For a complete discussion on the availability of P in biosolids, as well as the dynamics of P in biosolids-amended soils, the reader is referred to Torri et al. (2017).

157 for each scenario to fill this gap (see section E of the supplementary file). On the contrary, due to the much
158 more stable N content in sludge, a replacement ratio of 0.5 was used for N (Foley et al. 2010), which is a
159 ratio widely used in LCA studies (Heimersson et al. 2016). Sludge stabilization treatments may also
160 influence the plant availability of chemical sludge. To the best of our knowledge, only one study (Alvarenga
161 et al. 2017) has tackled the effect of anaerobic digestion (AD) on the P availability of biosolids deriving from
162 chemical precipitation and there, the effect of AD was reported as not significant. Moreover, if biosolids had
163 undergone thermal stabilization during composting, metal-bound P minerals in biosolids is considerably
164 reduced and, consequently, the release of available P is restricted (Hogan et al. 2001). Therefore, based on
165 the reasoning above, we have assumed that the stabilization processes of biosolids produced at the Carbonera
166 WWTP before the application to agriculture (i.e., AD followed by sludge composting) will not alter the P
167 availability. The corresponding synthetic fertilisers considered for substitution were ammonium sulphate
168 $((\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4)$ and diammonium phosphate $((\text{NH}_4)_2\text{HPO}_4)$ as the generic N and P_2O_5 sources, respectively
169 (Rodriguez-Garcia et al. 2011).²

170

171 **2.4. Life cycle impact assessment**

172 SimaPro v8.1 software was used for the impact assessment. Excluding global warming potential (GWP),
173 where the last version of the IPCC method (for a 100-year time horizon) (IPCC 2013) was used, impacts
174 were assessed using the Hierarchist ReCiPe(H) (v1.08) which is based on common policy principles
175 including the frame (Goedkoop et al. 2008a). Although endpoint results may be perceived more relevant for
176 decision-making, midpoint assessment directly relates the inventory results into environmental impacts.
177 Moreover, the use of endpoint indicators relies on additional assumptions and introduces greater uncertainty
178 in the modelling process compared to midpoint indicators (Corominas et al. 2013). Therefore, the ReCiPe
179 midpoint method was selected as it complies with all essential aspects for human toxicity (EC-JRC 2011)
180 and includes terrestrial ecotoxicity (Goedkoop et al. 2008a). However, human toxicity assessment is also
181 advised to be estimated using USEtox (Hauschild et al. 2013), hence we also applied the USEtox method
182 (Rosenbaum et al. 2008) solely for the human toxicity, and the results are presented in section H of the
183 supplementary file. Other impacts covered in this study are ozone depletion, terrestrial acidification,
184 photochemical oxidant formation and particular matter formation. Although these impact categories have

² Note that diammonium phosphate provides also N, which has been taken into consideration when calculating the avoided fertilisers.

185 gained less attention than the others discussed above, they are becoming a standard in the LCA studies (Zang
186 et al. 2015). Land-use related environmental indicators were excluded for their limited relevance in the
187 wastewater treatment sector (Zang et al. 2015). Furthermore, resource depletion categories were excluded
188 since these impacts are not well defined and modelled in LCA methodologies (Hauschild et al. 2013), and
189 there is still no globally agreed method that is sufficiently robust (Drielsma et al. 2016).

190 Finally, to show the environmental trade-offs between avoided impact due to wastewater treatment and
191 generated impact by the WWTP's life cycle, the net environmental benefit (NEB) approach (Godin et al.
192 2012) was also applied and the results are presented in section G of the supplementary file.

193

194 **2.5. Uncertainty analysis**

195 The importance to test and statically evaluate the environmental impacts in the LCA context has been
196 reported (Nhu et al. 2016). This is particular crucial in the wastewater treatment sector where the large data
197 variability and input data coverage can heavily influence the LCA results (Yoshida et al. 2014). Different
198 types of uncertainty include those relating to parameters (e.g., inaccuracies in measurement, mismatch
199 between the representativeness and use of data, and variability resulting from horizontal averaging), and
200 those concerning the LCA model (e.g., the uncertainties of the characterization factors) and the scenario
201 choices (e.g., choice of functional unit or characterization/weighing methods) (Huijbregts 2002). In this
202 study, we will mainly focus on data uncertainty but will also discuss briefly the influence of some model and
203 scenario choices (section H and G of the supplementary file, respectively). When an uncertainty calculation
204 is performed, it is also important to keep track of the correlations in the data (Nhu et al. 2016). Two kinds of
205 correlation can be identified: (1) correlations between process chains of production systems and (2)
206 correlations within a process record. In this study, only the type of correlation between process chains of
207 production systems is considered, as a comparison Monte Carlo is carried out with SimaPro (in which such
208 issues are excluded).

209 Based on the uncertainty of the life cycle inventory (LCI) data expressed as probability distributions (see
210 Table S.7 of the supplementary file), the Monte Carlo simulations were run with 1,000 iterations at a
211 significance level of 95%. Clearly, the output distributions generated by any Monte Carlo simulation, and
212 any conclusion derived therefrom, are sensitive to the choice of input distribution. In the current study, when
213 the class of distribution was known a priori we proceeded with direct estimation of the parameters of the

214 distribution (e.g., mean, standard deviation). If the class of the distribution was unknown, default
215 distributions were consulted for possible use based on the range of possible values (Lipton et al. 1995).

216

217 **2.6. Life cycle cost**

218 In general, costs can be divided into capital and operational costs. The capital cost was estimated by
219 summing the construction, mechanical instrument and consulting costs, as obtained from the WWTP
220 operation office (see Table S.6 of the supplementary file). As major operating costs, the electricity and
221 chemical consumptions, sludge disposal and staff costs were considered. In order to share the same time
222 boundary as the LCA, the time value of money is considered. Net present value (NPV) was adopted as an
223 indicator to evaluate the economic performance of the different scenarios. The NPV for wastewater
224 treatment was calculated based on Eq. (1):

$$225 \text{ NPV} = \text{CAPEX} + \sum_n \frac{\text{OPEX}}{(1+i)^n}, \quad (1)$$

226 Where CAPEX and OPEX denote capital cost and operational cost, respectively, i refers to discount rate
227 adjusted for inflation, equal to 5% (this is a compromise figure based on market interest rate, cost of capital
228 and time preference considerations (Hermelink and de Jager 2015)), and n represents years.

229 Furthermore, in order to share the same functional unit as the LCA, the total cost is divided into LCC per FU
230 (1 kg PO₄ eq. removed).

231

232 **3. Results**

233 **3.1. Inventory analysis**

234 An overview of the LCI of the treatment options under analysis is reported in Table S.3 of the supplementary
235 file. Once SCENA was operating, the electricity consumed per kg of N removed was reduced from 7.51 kWh
236 in the main line to 3.21 kWh in the side stream. This is consequence of the joint effects of a more efficient N
237 removal pathway (i.e., via nitrite compared to complete nitrification in the main line) and aeration system
238 (i.e., superfine bubble diffusers as opposed to coarse bubble diffusers in the main line), which make
239 removing N in the side stream more convenient. Besides, energy consumed for aeration in the main line can
240 also be further reduced by about 20% due to the implementation of CAPS and RBS systems (sc. 2B and 2C,

241 respectively), since they can increase the organic matter recovered from wastewater, thus resulting in a
242 reduced COD load entering the biological bioreactor of the main line.

243 On a process level, the via-nitrite N removal in the scSBR improved the effluent quality of the WWTP in
244 terms of total nitrogen (Table 2), while the benefits regarding total phosphorus were less evident since the
245 additional P removal in the side stream is compensated for by a lower chemical P removal in the main line
246 (i.e., in order to maintain the required effluent quality, thus optimizing costs). However, sc. 2B is
247 characterized by a much better P effluent quality. This is a consequence of the fact that the CAPS system can
248 attain higher P removal (up to 70%) in the primary sedimentation tank due to a significantly higher dosage of
249 poly aluminium chloride (PAC) (Table S.3).

250 For sc. 0, N₂O emissions were found to be approximately 4.55 kgN-N₂O/d that represents 1.16% of the N
251 influent load. Compared with previous studies (see for example Kampschreur et al. (2009)), N₂O emissions
252 were remarkably high at the Carbonera WWTP. Some operational features employed during the process, i.e.,
253 intermittent aeration of the activated sludge process, have been identified as possible features promoting N₂O
254 emissions. However, our emission factor is in accordance with the outcomes for long-term online
255 measurement campaign carried out at the Viikinmaki WWTP³, which presented an emission factor of 1.9%
256 for influent N (Kosonen et al. 2016). In the scSBR of the SCENA system, the N₂O emissions were 1.42% of
257 the N influent load of the side-stream line, which is in accordance with the range of 0.24-1.49% previously
258 measured by Frison et al. (2015). Moreover, the N₂O emissions were comparable with values in the literature
259 for biological systems accomplishing N removal via partial nitrification/anammox (Schaubroeck et al. 2015).
260 Thus, shifting N removal from the main stream to the side stream of the WWTP did not increase N₂O
261 emissions as one might expect due to the higher risk of nitrite accumulation.

262

263 **3.2. Life cycle impact assessment of the treatment options**

264 By integrating the recommendation of Zang et al. (2015), the results are grouped into the following:
265 freshwater and marine eutrophication (Fig. 2); global warming potential (Fig. 3); toxicity and terrestrial
266 ecotoxicity (Fig. 4); and ozone depletion, photochemical oxidant formation, particular matter formation, and
267 terrestrial acidification (Fig. 5). All the impacts are expressed per kg of PO₄ eq. removed.

³ The process scheme of the Viikinmaki WWTP is different in comparison to the Carbonera WWTP. At Viikinmaki the biological reactions are carried out in six consecutive reactors, while at the Carbonera WWTP, aerated and anoxic phases are performed in the same reactor. However, the two WWTPs share similar operational features, e.g., fluctuating influent flow and intermittent aeration at the activated sludge process.

268

269 **3.2.1. Eutrophication potential**

270 Eutrophication has been emphasized by earlier studies and is still considered the most relevant impact
271 category when performing environmental evaluation of WWTPs (Corominas et al. 2013, Zang et al. 2015).
272 Thus, is especially important here as eutrophication impacts can be reduced immediately by implementing
273 side-stream treatment technologies to enhance the nutrient removal efficiency. As expected, the impact of
274 wastewater treatment on eutrophication is dominated by the effluent discharge and the nutrient-related
275 emissions during compost land application (Fig. 2).

276 After the implementation of SCENA, a reduction of 27% of the marine eutrophication has been found (sc. 1)
277 as a consequence of the better effluent quality with respect to N compounds (e.g., NH₄ and NO₃), which
278 could also be further reduced (by an additional 18%) with the optimization of SCENA (sc. 2A-C). The
279 benefits in terms of freshwater eutrophication are less evident since following the installation of the SCENA
280 system the operation of the WWTP was adjusted to guarantee the same P effluent quality. Nevertheless, the
281 substitution of the primary clarification with the CAPS system (sc. 2B) would imply a much lower P in the
282 effluent thanks to the additional dosage of PAC, which translates in the reduction by 43% of the freshwater
283 eutrophication.

284 Finally, a considerable portion of the marine eutrophication impact (19-21% depending of the scenario) is
285 represented by the N emissions due to land application.

286

287 **3.2.2. Global warming potential**

288 Impacts on this category are associated mainly with electricity use and direct gaseous emissions during
289 wastewater treatment (Fig. 3).

290 For sc. 0, electricity accounts for 35% of the total impact and the total plant greenhouse gas (GHG)
291 emissions for 56%. According to our measurements, the N₂O emissions comprised 80% of the total
292 emissions, which is in line with the results reported by Kosonen et al. (2016). Remaining impacts are
293 characterized as follow: composting (4.5%), effluent release (2.3%), transport (1.5%) and production of
294 chemicals used (1.3%). On the beneficial side, i.e., mitigating effects, two elements from compost
295 application to land are contributing here: C sequestration and avoided fertilizers, accounting for 4.1% and
296 1.9% of the total impact, respectively.

297 The reduction of electricity consumption and N₂O emissions translates to a reduction of about 14% of GWP,
298 respectively with the following shares: 27% and 65%. The additional energy saving in sc. 2A could further
299 decrease the GWP up to an additional 4%. In terms of avoiding the impact from offset fertilizers, sc. 1 did
300 not show any improvement as the SCENA system was not yet optimized for P removal (Table 2). When the
301 potential optimization is evaluated, the additional P removal in the side stream achieved in sc. 2A results in a
302 lower PAC consumption (12%) in the main line and in a higher P recovered in biosolids (8%) that leads to a
303 benefit from avoided fertilizer. On the contrary, the increased P removal by the CAPS configuration (sc. 2B)
304 did not increase the amount of fertilizer avoided since the P recovered by the chemical process is not
305 available for plant uptake. Besides, sc. 2B and 2C do not result in a net benefit over the other configurations,
306 since their advantages (i.e., better performance of the SBFR and lower energy consumption for aeration)
307 were balanced by the higher chemical consumption in sc. 2B and a slightly higher energy consumption of the
308 RBS system in sc. 2C.

309

310 **3.2.3. Human toxicity and terrestrial ecotoxicity**

311 Direct emissions of heavy metals dominate toxicity-related impact categories, accounting for half of the total
312 impact of human toxicity and almost the entire impact of terrestrial ecotoxicity (Fig. 4). Once SCENA was
313 up and running, no large variations took place in heavy metals behaviour, which are mostly attributable to
314 anthropogenic activities anyway, such as traffic emissions and weather characteristics (Peña-Fernández et al.
315 2015). In fact, the lower impact of terrestrial ecotoxicity reported for sc. 1 and followings is principally due
316 to the better effluent quality achieved (i.e., higher FU). Emissions from transport of biosolids increase the
317 human toxicity impact; however, these are overcome by the avoided contaminants due to fertilisers'
318 replacement and their correspondent production. Moreover, emissions associated with chemical manufacture
319 increase the human toxicity and hence shifting P removal from chemical precipitation to biological removal
320 by SCENA entails an additional advantage.

321

322 **3.2.4. Other impact categories**

323 The impact linked to ozone depletion mainly occurs due to the electricity production and to a lesser extent to
324 transport and chemical manufacturing (Fig 5a). Consequently, implementing SCENA reduced the ozone
325 depletion potential by 9% (sc. 1), which can be further reduced (up to 14%) by sc. 2A and 2B. However, the

326 beneficial effects generated by avoiding fertilizers and chemicals use are offset by emissions from transport
327 of biosolids.

328 The photochemical oxidant and particular matter formation potentials (Fig. 5b and 5c, respectively) reflect
329 the difference between the impacts due to the electricity and chemicals use for the wastewater treatment and
330 the ones avoided thanks to the land application of biosolids. As seen for ozone depletion, implementing
331 energy efficiency with SCENA is beneficial also for these impact categories. Sc. 1 reduces the
332 photochemical oxidant formation potential by 9%. Furthermore, the increasing of P recovery in sc. 2A has
333 the potential to reduce the impact for the same category up to 13%.

334 The particular matter formation and terrestrial acidification (Fig. 5d) follow the trend observed for the
335 photochemical oxidant formation potential, even if in sc. 1 the ammonia emissions from the anaerobic
336 supernatant storage tank increased the particular matter formation and terrestrial acidification impacts.
337 Connecting this plant section to the air treatment system may mitigate these impacts; however, until this is
338 done, these emissions will likely continue to be an issue. For the other scenarios (2A-C), the ammonia
339 emissions may be offset by eliminating the gravity thickener of the digested sludge. Another source of
340 contamination derives from flaring the biogas; this impact contributes about 5% to the particular matter
341 formation potential, and is similar for the different scenarios.

342

343 **3.2.5. Uncertainty analysis**

344 In Fig. 6, the summation of both blue and grey bars for each category is equal to 100%. The negative portion
345 to the left (blue bars) represents the percentage of cases where $\text{impact}_{\text{AssessedScenario}} \geq \text{impact}_{\text{BaseScenario}}$ while
346 grey bars to the right, or the positive portion, represent the inverse situation ($\text{impact}_{\text{AssessedScenario}} <$
347 $\text{impact}_{\text{BaseScenario}}$), being the BaseScenario the sc. 0. This allows understanding whether the differences shown
348 in Fig. 2, 3, 4 and 5 are significant. In general, we can assume that if 90% of the Monte Carlo runs are
349 favourable, the difference may be considered significant (Goedkoop et al. 2008b).

350 The Monte Carlo simulations suggest that all the scenarios perform better in terms of GWP compared to sc.
351 0, with Monte Carlo frequency highest for sc. 2B (98.5%), followed by sc. 2A (97.6%), sc. 2C (95.8%) and
352 sc. 1 (92.8%). Regarding eutrophication, the results are less clear, especially in terms of freshwater
353 eutrophication. This is due to the already mentioned compensation effect in total P removal in order to
354 maintain the same quality effluent and, consequently, the role of SCENA was favourable at lower Monte

355 Carlo frequencies of 55-83% and 75-88% with respect to freshwater eutrophication and marine
356 eutrophication, respectively. The benefits of SCENA (e.g., lower energy consumption for N removal and
357 chemical consumption for P removal) are more evident in the fossil-based electricity and chemicals related
358 impact categories, such as ozone depletion (favourable at Monte Carlo frequencies of 86-97%). Among the
359 toxicity-related impact categories, human toxicity shows the highest uncertainty. Even if the negative
360 impacts of these categories are reduced per FU, after the uncertainty analysis robust conclusions could not be
361 drawn on the effect of the SCENA system. This can be explained by the fact that the concentration of heavy
362 metals in the final sludge and the treated effluent is not influenced by SCENA. Although the LCA results
363 show that SCENA is also beneficial in terms of photochemical oxidant formation, particular matter
364 formation and terrestrial acidification, the inclusion of the uncertainty revealed that these differences are
365 favourable with lower Monte Carlo frequencies with respect to GWP. In short, the uncertainty analysis
366 revealed sc. 2A as the most environmentally friendly scenario, having lower impacts for most of the
367 categories with confident level of 90%.

368

369 **3.3. Economic analysis**

370 Results from the LCC are categorized as investment cost and operational cost, such as cost for electricity and
371 chemical provision, cost for sludge compost and disposal and labour costs (Table 3), and identify sc. 2B as
372 the option with the highest cost per FU (5.75 €).

373 From an economic perspective, the inclusion of SCENA in the side stream (sc. 1) reduces costs by about 3%
374 per FU, which can be further reduced (up to 5%) by sc. 2A thanks to a further reduction in electricity
375 consumption for aeration and chemical consumption for chemical P removal. Conversely, sc. 2B and 2C
376 increase the total cost due to higher PAC dosing. The investment cost for each scenario does not make a big
377 difference, apart for sc. 2C that is slighter higher, and it is almost negligible in comparison with the
378 operational cost (between 1% and 3% of the total cost). Regarding the cost distribution, this is uniform
379 among the different scenarios under study. On average, 48% of the total cost is associated with energy
380 consumption, 27% with sludge management, 16% with labour and the remaining 7% with chemicals
381 provision. The further reduction of energy use for aeration in sc. 2B and 2C is compensated for by the
382 additional cost of sludge management, which makes these scenarios not recommendable unless energy
383 recovery from the increased biogas production is guaranteed (which is not done at the moment). Moreover,

384 for sc. 2B the additional chemical use of the CAPS configuration has the double drawback of increasing cost
385 for chemical consumption as well as contributing to an increase in the amount of chemical sludge to be
386 disposed of, and as consequence also the cost for its management.

387

388 **4. Discussion**

389 **4.1. Energy efficiency improvements**

390 One of the aims of upgrading the sludge line with side-stream treatment is to improve the energy efficiency
391 of the WWTP. The measurements show lower electricity consumption at a process level, due to a lower need
392 for aeration in the scSBR compared to the main biological reactor. The reduction of electricity consumption
393 per kg N removed for sc. 1 was 57%, which led on a system level to a reduction of the total consumption of
394 about 12%. The fact that about half of the total costs are associated with energy use makes once more
395 evident the importance of energy efficiency both from an economic and an environmental point of view.

396 Although the integration of SCENA in the side stream has proved to be a good example of energy efficiency
397 improvement, energy self-sufficiency is still a challenge at the Carbonera WWTP. Fully energy self-
398 sufficient WWTPs are possible through improving the energy efficiency as well as harvesting energy from
399 the biogas (Gu et al. 2017). Electrical energy autarchy is already reported to have been achieved for the
400 Strass WWTP (Schaubroeck et al. 2015), where the largest electricity saving was provided through the
401 addition of a co-substrate to the anaerobic digester (e.g., kitchen waste and fat). At the Carbonera WWTP the
402 biogas produced is used only for heating the digester, while the excess is burnt in a torch. However, in light
403 of the fact that after the implementation of SCENA about 10% of the mixed sludge is sent to the fermenter of
404 the SCENA system for the VFAs production, the anaerobic digester is now underexploited. Therefore, the
405 addition of a co-substrate in the digester would imply a better usage of the plant's infrastructure, which could
406 help the Carbonera WWTP moving forward towards energy self-sufficiency, as well as mitigating the
407 negative environmental impacts due to energy use. Finally, it should be noted that when implementing
408 SCENA within a WWTP that uses biogas for electricity production, a reduction of the energy produced
409 should be considered as it might partially offset the energy savings due to SCENA. In this case, when
410 evaluating the WWTP upgrading, the methane yield of the post-fermented sludge should be measured to
411 evaluate the possibility to recycle the residual sludge from the SBFR to the digester, thus limiting the
412 reduction in biogas production.

413

414 **4.2. Environmental performance improvements**

415 The eutrophication potential impact can be decreased immediately by implementing more sophisticated
416 technologies to enhance the nutrient removal (however, generally associated with increase in other
417 environmental impacts) (Zang et al. 2015). For example, Rodriguez-Garcia et al. (2014) found a substantial
418 reduction of eutrophication associated with side-stream treatments. However, they stated that to reduce
419 significantly the nutrient load of the effluent, side-stream N-removal technologies must be followed by
420 struvite crystallization for P removal, at the cost of increasing electricity and chemical use, which implies
421 higher costs and GWP impacts. In this sense SCENA represents a convenient alternative as it combines N
422 and P biological removal in a single system, which can optimize use of electricity and chemicals. Also
423 Hauck et al. (2016) reported a 16% reduction of eutrophication after the implementation of a two-step
424 anammox in the side stream. This is in line with our findings for marine eutrophication (22-39% depending
425 of the scenario).

426 In terms of GWP, other elements contribute besides electricity consumption and there is a certain consensus
427 in the literature on the importance of N₂O emissions, which can be more important than electricity use
428 (Schaubroeck et al. 2015, Hauck et al. 2016). At the Carbonera WWTP, shifting N removal from the main
429 line to the side stream has the advantage of reducing the N₂O emissions in the main line as result of more
430 favourable process conditions in the biological reactor of the mainline, i.e., a higher degree of N removal and
431 more stable conditions (Parravicini et al. 2016).

432 The total heavy metals load of untreated wastewater ends up in the sludge or remains in the treated effluent,
433 as consequence no metal biodegradation is achieved during the wastewater treatment. The Carbonera WWTP
434 is a significant source of heavy metals to both aquatic and terrestrial recipients. The impact of terrestrial
435 ecotoxicity was found to exceed the benefit of avoided fertilizers. The latter was already acknowledged in
436 the literature (Schaubroeck et al. 2015).

437 Finally, it can be seen that the impact categories of ozone depletion, photochemical oxidant formation,
438 particular matter formation, and terrestrial acidification are mostly attributed to the consumption of
439 electricity and chemicals, and thus the results reveal an improvement in the environmental performance of
440 the new layout compared to the old configuration.

441

442 **4.3. Phosphorus considerations on land application of biosolids**

443 Selecting a P replacement ratio is challenging and especially important in this study where the additional
444 biological P removal by SCENA is expected to reduce the intensity of the chemical P removal. The
445 prediction of the P fertilizer value from sludge characteristics is possible through modelling. For example,
446 Falk Øgaard and Brod (2016) developed a multiple linear regression model to predict the P fertilizer value
447 using Fe and Al content in activated sludge as predictors and reported a significant negative effect of both Al
448 and Fe on the fertilization effect. The results of this study contribute considerably to the understanding of P
449 availability in biosolids. However, we were not able to check for the model prediction accuracy due to data
450 unavailability.

451 The results of the P replacement ratio estimation are reported in Table 2. Apart from sc. 2B, these values are
452 in line with the values commonly used in the literature (50-70%). Sludge containing high levels of P does not
453 necessarily imply a greater potential for P supply. In sc. 2B, the dosage of PAC used for the increasing of the
454 organic matter recovery has the additional effect of increasing the total P removal from 54% to 73%
455 (compared to sc. 1). Much more P is recovered in this scenario, even if the majority is in the form of
456 aluminium phosphate, and hence not available for plant uptake. Furthermore, as a result of the higher organic
457 matter removal (through the CAPS system) the growth activities of activated sludge are also reduced (and as
458 a consequence the P removal) in comparison to the other scenarios. For these reasons, the P availability of
459 biosolids in sc. 2B is only 9.5%. These findings are in line with Falk Øgaard and Brod (2016) who
460 demonstrated that the concentration of the precipitation salts in sludge are inversely correlated with the P
461 fertilization effect of sludge. Thus, considering that an economically feasible process for recovering P from
462 metal salt compounds does not yet exist (Wilfert et al. 2015), these results suggest that in the perspective of
463 P recovery from wastewater, biological P removal should be preferred to a chemical process if the destiny of
464 the sludge produced during treatment is land application to agriculture.

465

466 **5. Conclusions**

467 Updates to process improvements of existing WWTP, i.e., integration of SCENA as side-stream treatment,
468 imply changes in the plant operating conditions that affect effluent and sludge quality, electricity and
469 chemical use, GHG emissions and total cost. Hence, this study emphasizes the need to evaluate all of these

470 elements by means of a holistic approach based on environmental and economic indicators. The main
471 findings of the study are:

- 472 • SCENA was identified as a more sustainable option for providing a greater degree of environmental
473 protection at lower cost. In particular, SCENA induced significant improvement in terms of (i)
474 reduction of GHG emissions, mainly due to increased energy efficiency, (ii) reduction of
475 eutrophication, due to a higher level of N abatement and (iii) reduction of total cost, due to the lower
476 amounts of electricity and chemicals consumed.
- 477 • Moreover, the performance of the Carbonera WWTP can be further improved if the operation of the
478 whole plant is optimized, i.e., substituting gravitational with mechanical thickening of the sludge (sc.
479 2B). Although a significant reduction of freshwater eutrophication as well as further energy savings
480 could be obtained changing the operational strategy to the chemically enhanced primary treatment,
481 due to the higher consumption of chemicals the operational cost will increase by 5%.
- 482 • The uncertainty analysis proved the validity of the LCA results for GWP and impact categories
483 related to the consumption of fossil-based electricity and chemicals, while robust conclusions could
484 not be drawn on freshwater eutrophication and toxicity-related impact categories.
- 485 • From a methodological point of view, the suggested method for the estimation of the P availability
486 of biosolids, in contrast to the classical approach consisting in the application of a fixed P
487 replacement ratio, provided a better picture of the real situation and revealed that improving P
488 recovery by chemical precipitation does not give rise to an environmental benefit by replacement of
489 synthetic fertilizer.
- 490 • Although results from different LCA studies depend on the assumptions, this case study confirms the
491 dominant role of N₂O emissions on the GWP and emphasizes once again that more consideration
492 should be paid to N₂O emissions at WWTPs.

493 The conclusions presented here have partially motivated the Horizon 2020 ‘SMART-Plant’ action⁴, which
494 will allow for the optimization of the best scenario for SCENA integration in the Carbonera WWTP.

495

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⁴ www.smart-plant.eu

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504

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